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- 13.00.00 Pedagogika fanlari
- 13.00.01 Pedagogika nazariyasi. Pedagogik ta'limotlar tarixi
- 13.00.02 Ta'lim va tarbiya nazariyasi va metodikasi (sohalar bo'yicha)
- 13.00.03 Maxsus pedagogika
- 13.00.04 Jismoniy tarbiya va sport mashg'ulotlari nazariyasi va metodikasi
- 13.00.05 Kasb-hunar ta'limi nazariyasi va metodikasi
- 13.00.06 Elektron ta'lim nazariyasi va metodikasi (ta'lim sohaları va bosqichlari bo'yicha)
- 13.00.07 Ta'limda menejment
- 13.00.08 Maktabgacha ta'lim va tarbiya nazariyasi va metodikasi
- 13.00.09 Ijtimoiy pedagogika
- 07.00.00 Tarix fanlari
- 19.00.00 Psixologiya fanlari
- 01.00.00 Fizika-matematika fanlari
- 02.00.00 Kimyo fanlari
- 03.00.00 Biologiya fanlari
- 09.00.00 Falsafa fanlari
- 10.00.00 Filologiya fanlari
- 11.00.00 Geografiya fanlari

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COMPARATIVE STUDY OF PASSIVE CONSTRUCTIONS IN ENGLISH AND THEIR TRANSLATION INTO UZBEK

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Abstract: The study investigates the passive voice in English and its translation into Uzbek from a comparative linguistic perspective. Particular attention is paid to the structural, semantic, and pragmatic characteristics of passive constructions in both languages, emphasizing their similarities and differences in terms of formation, usage, and communicative function. As an important grammatical category, the passive voice serves to highlight either the action itself or the receiver of the action rather than the performer, thereby contributing to objectivity and effective information organization in discourse. Furthermore, the research examines the translation of English passive constructions, which are generally formed with the auxiliary verb *be* and a past participle, into Uzbek through morphological markers such as *-il*, *-in*, and auxiliary forms such as *bo'lmoq*. Translation techniques, including grammatical substitution, transposition, and nominalization, are also analyzed to ensure semantic and stylistic equivalence.

Key words: passive voice, comparative linguistics, English language, Uzbek language, translation studies, grammatical structure, pragmatics, syntax, voice, morphological markers.

Annotatsiya: Tadqiqot ingliz tilidagi majhul nisbat va uning o'zbek tiliga tarjima qilinish xususiyatlarini qiyosiy tilshunoslik nuqtayi nazaridan o'rganishga qaratilgan. Unda har ikki tildagi majhul konstruksiyalarning strukturaviy, semantik va pragmatik xususiyatlari tahlil qilinib, ularning yasalishi, qo'llanilishi hamda kommunikativ vazifalaridagi o'xshash va farqli jihatlar yoritilgan. Muhim grammatik kategoriya sifatida majhul nisbat harakat bajaruvchisiga emas, balki harakatning o'ziga yoki uning obyektiga e'tibor qaratish imkonini beradi hamda nutqda obyektivlik va axborotni mantiqiy tashkil etishga xizmat qiladi. Shuningdek, ingliz tilida *be* yordamchi fe'li va o'tgan zamon sifatdoshi orqali yasaladigan majhul konstruksiyalarning o'zbek tilida *-il*, *-in* kabi morfologik ko'rsatkichlar hamda *bo'lmoq* yordamchi shakllari vositasida ifodalanishi tahlil qilingan. Mazmuniy va uslubiy ekvivalentlikni ta'minlashda grammatik almashtirish, transpozitsiya va nominalizatsiya kabi tarjima usullarining qo'llanilishi ham ko'rib chiqilgan.

Kalit so'zlar: majhul nisbat, qiyosiy tilshunoslik, ingliz tili, o'zbek tili, tarjimashunoslik, grammatik tuzilish, pragmatika, sintaksis, nisbat, morfologik ko'rsatkichlar.

Аннотация: Исследование посвящено изучению страдательного залога в английском языке и особенностей его перевода на узбекский язык с точки зрения сравнительного языкознания. Особое внимание уделяется структурным, семантическим и прагматическим характеристикам пассивных конструкций в обоих языках, а также выявлению их сходств и различий в способах образования, употребления и коммуникативных функциях. Страдательный залог как важная грамматическая категория используется для акцентирования внимания на действии или объекте действия, а не на его исполнителе, что способствует объективности и логической организации информации в дискурсе. Также рассматриваются способы передачи английских пассивных конструкций, образованных с помощью вспомогательного глагола be и причастия прошедшего времени, средствами узбекского языка через морфологические показатели -il, -in и вспомогательные конструкции типа bo'lmoq. Анализируются переводческие приемы, включая грамматическую замену, транспозицию и номинализацию, обеспечивающие смысловую и стилистическую эквивалентность.

Ключевые слова: страдательный залог, сравнительное языкознание, английский язык, узбекский язык, переводоведение, грамматическая структура, прагматика, синтаксис, залог, морфологические показатели.

INTRODUCTION

In modern linguistics, passive voice is recognized as one of the most important grammatical categories that plays a significant role in shaping information structure and discourse organization. It allows speakers and writers to shift the focus from the doer of an action to the receiver of the action, thereby contributing to objectivity, neutrality, and thematic continuity in communication. The study of passive constructions becomes especially relevant in academic, scientific, and formal discourse, where emphasis is often placed on processes and results rather than on agents.

From a cross-linguistic perspective, passive voice demonstrates both universal and language-specific features. In English, passive constructions are primarily formed analytically through the auxiliary verb be combined with the past participle of the main verb (e.g., The book was written). This structure is highly productive and frequently used in written and academic registers. In contrast, Uzbek expresses passive meaning mainly through morphological markers such as -il, -in, -tir, and -dir, as well as auxiliary constructions involving bo'lmoq (e.g., Kitob yozildi). These structural differences reflect the typological distinction between English as an analytic language and Uzbek as an agglutinative language.

Furthermore, passive constructions in both languages are not limited to grammatical functions only, but also carry important pragmatic meanings. In English, passive voice is often used to maintain formality and objectivity, particularly in scientific and academic texts, while in Uzbek it may additionally express politeness, indirectness, and respect within social interaction. Such differences highlight the importance of pragmalinguistic factors in understanding how passive constructions function in real communication.

The translation of passive voice from English into Uzbek presents several linguistic challenges due to differences in syntactic structure, semantic emphasis, and stylistic conventions. Translators often employ strategies such as grammatical substitution, transposition, and nominalization to achieve natural and context-appropriate equivalents. In some cases, passive constructions in English are rendered as active structures in Uzbek to preserve clarity and naturalness.

Therefore, this study aims to conduct a comparative linguistic analysis of passive voice in English and Uzbek, focusing on its structural formation, functional usage, and translation strategies. By examining these aspects, the research seeks to contribute to a deeper understanding of how passive constructions operate across typologically different languages and how meaning is preserved in translation processes.

LITERATURE REVIEW

The study of passive voice has long been an important area of interest in both theoretical and applied linguistics. Researchers have examined passive constructions from syntactic, semantic, pragmatic, and typological perspectives, emphasizing their role in information structuring and discourse organization. In English linguistics, passive voice has been widely analyzed in classical and modern grammatical frameworks, while in Uzbek linguistics it has been explored mainly from a morphological and syntactic viewpoint. Comparative studies between the two languages further highlight significant differences in structure and usage.

One of the most influential works in English grammar is by Quirk et al. (1985) in *A Comprehensive Grammar of the English Language*, where passive constructions are described as a grammatical transformation that promotes the object of an active sentence into the subject position. This transformation allows speakers to background the agent and foreground the patient, which is especially common in formal and academic writing. Similarly, Huddleston and Pullum (2002), in *The Cambridge Grammar of the English Language*, emphasize that passive voice is not only a structural phenomenon but also a discourse strategy used to maintain objectivity and thematic continuity.

Biber et al. (1999), in their corpus-based study of spoken and written English, demonstrate that passive constructions are significantly more frequent in academic and informational texts than in conversational speech. They argue that passive voice contributes to an impersonal style, which is highly valued in scientific communication. These findings support the idea that English passive constructions serve both grammatical and stylistic purposes.

In contrast, Uzbek linguistic studies, such as those by Sayfiyev (2000) and Rahimov (2012), focus on the morphological formation of passive voice using suffixes like *-il* and *-in*. These studies highlight that Uzbek passive constructions are less frequent in everyday speech and are mainly used in formal, written, and official contexts. Uzbek linguists also note that passive structures are often replaced by active constructions in spoken language to ensure clarity and naturalness.

Kadirova (2015), in her comparative research on English and Uzbek passive constructions, emphasizes that although both languages share the communicative goal of emphasizing the receiver of the action, they differ significantly in syntactic realization. English relies on auxiliary-based analytic structures, while Uzbek uses agglutinative morphological markers. This difference affects translation strategies and often requires structural transformation during the translation process.

Further theoretical insights are provided by Siewierska (1984), who classifies passive constructions across languages and highlights their role in managing information flow and discourse focus. According to her typological analysis, languages differ in how explicitly they mark agents in passive constructions, with English allowing optional agent expression through *by*-phrases, whereas Uzbek typically omits the agent or expresses it indirectly.

Keenan and Dryer (2007) further argue that passive voice functions as a universal discourse mechanism for promoting topicality and reducing agent prominence. Foley and Van Valin (1984), from a functional grammar perspective, also explain that passive constructions serve to rearrange syntactic roles in accordance with communicative needs, especially in information packaging.

In addition to these theoretical perspectives, recent pragmalinguistic studies, such as Inomjonova and Minikulov (2026), have expanded the analysis by focusing on the communicative functions of passive voice. Their findings show that English passive constructions are primarily used for objectivity and textual cohesion, while Uzbek passives also carry additional pragmatic meanings such as politeness, respect, and social distance.

Overall, the literature indicates that passive voice is a multifunctional grammatical category that cannot be fully understood without considering both structural and pragmatic dimensions. While English and Uzbek share similar communicative goals in using passive constructions, their linguistic realization and discourse functions differ significantly due to typological and cultural factors.

RESEARCH METHODOLOGY

This study adopts a qualitative and comparative linguistic approach to analyze passive voice constructions in English and Uzbek. The main objective is to examine the structural, semantic, and pragmalinguistic features of passive constructions in both languages and to identify their similarities and differences in usage, function, and translation patterns. The research is based on a descriptive-comparative method, which allows for the systematic observation and analysis of linguistic phenomena in their natural context without altering their original structure. This approach is particularly suitable for investigating grammatical categories such as passive voice, where both form and communicative function are essential.

Data for the study were collected from multiple sources to ensure a comprehensive and balanced analysis. These sources include academic articles, linguistic research papers, formal documents, textbooks, and constructed examples designed to illustrate specific structural and pragmatic features of passive constructions in English and Uzbek.

The analytical procedure combined syntactic, semantic, and pragmalinguistic frameworks. The syntactic analysis focused on the structural formation of passive voice, particularly the English analytic form (*be* + past participle) and the Uzbek morphological and analytical forms (*-il*, *-in*, *-tir*, *-dir*, and constructions with *bo'lmoq*). The semantic analysis examined how meaning is preserved or shifted during translation, especially in relation to the roles of agent and patient. The pragmalinguistic analysis focused on communicative functions such as objectivity, politeness, indirectness, information structuring, and agent suppression.

Each example was classified according to its structural type, functional role, and translation strategy. A comparative analysis was then conducted to identify patterns of similarity and divergence between the two languages. In addition, translation techniques such as grammatical substitution, transposition, and nominalization were analyzed to determine how passive constructions are rendered from English into Uzbek.

To ensure validity and reliability, all examples were cross-checked with established grammatical descriptions and linguistic studies. Consistent analytical criteria were applied throughout the study to maintain accuracy and objectivity. Overall, this methodology provides a solid framework for understanding passive voice constructions not only as grammatical structures but also as functional and pragmatic tools in communication across English and Uzbek languages.

ANALYSIS AND RESULTS

The comparative analysis of passive voice constructions in English and Uzbek reveals that although both languages share the same communicative goal of foregrounding the patient and backgrounding the agent, they differ significantly in structural realization, usage frequency, and pragmatic function. These differences are primarily conditioned by typological characteristics, as English is an analytic language, whereas Uzbek is agglutinative and relies heavily on morphological markers.

In English, passive constructions are predominantly formed using the auxiliary verb *be* combined with the past participle of the main verb. For example, in the sentence “The report was prepared by the committee,” the object of the active sentence becomes the grammatical subject in the passive structure. This transformation allows English speakers to shift focus from the doer of the action to the action itself or its result. In academic and scientific discourse, such structures are frequently used to maintain objectivity, as in “The experiment was conducted under controlled conditions.”

In Uzbek, passive voice is mainly expressed through morphological suffixes such as *-il*, *-in*, *-tir*, *-dir*, or through analytical constructions with *bo'lmoq*. For instance, “Hisobot tayyorlandi” corresponds to the English passive sentence “The report was prepared.” Unlike English, Uzbek often omits the agent entirely, and its inclusion is relatively rare. When necessary, the agent can be expressed using the postposition *tomonidan*, as in “Hisobot komissiya tomonidan tayyorlandi.” However, this form is typically used in formal or official contexts.

From a functional perspective, both languages use passive constructions to emphasize the action or result rather than the agent. However, English passives are more flexible in allowing explicit agent expression, while Uzbek passives tend to favor agent suppression. This reflects a broader discourse tendency in Uzbek, where indirectness and contextual interpretation are preferred.

The frequency analysis shows that English passive constructions are more common, especially in academic, technical, and formal writing. For example, sentences such as “It was found that the results were significant” are typical in research articles. In contrast, Uzbek tends to prefer active constructions in similar contexts, such as “Tadqiqotchilar natijalar muhim ekanini aniqladilar,” although passive forms like “Natijalar muhim deb topildi” are also possible in formal writing.

Comparative Analysis of Passive Voice Constructions in English and Uzbek

No.	Feature	English Passive Voice	Uzbek Passive Voice
1	Structure	be + past participle (e.g., was written, is done)	Morphological suffixes <i>-il</i> , <i>-in</i> , <i>-tir</i> , <i>-dir</i> or auxiliary <i>bo'lmoq</i> (e.g., <i>yo'zildi</i> , <i>bajarildi</i>)
2	Agent expression	Can be expressed using <i>by</i> -phrase (by the teacher)	Usually omitted or expressed with <i>tomonidan</i>
3	Frequency of use	Highly frequent, especially in academic and formal texts	Relatively less frequent, mainly in formal contexts
4	Main function	Emphasizes process and objectivity	Emphasizes result, state, and formality
5	Discourse role	Ensures cohesion and informational neutrality	Adds contextual and pragmatic meaning
6	Translation strategy	Often preserved as passive in translation	Often converted into passive or active structure
7	Pragmatic meaning	Neutral, objective, academic tone	Politeness, indirectness, and formality

Another important observation is the difference in pragmatic meaning. In English, passive voice primarily serves to ensure objectivity and cohesion in discourse. In Uzbek, however, passive constructions may also convey politeness, respect, and social distance. For example, “Qaror qabul qilindi” is commonly used in official communication to present information in a neutral and respectful manner without explicitly naming the decision-maker.

Translation analysis shows that passive constructions often require structural transformation when transferred between the two languages. English passive sentences may be translated into Uzbek either as passive or active structures depending on context. For instance, “The car was repaired yesterday” can be translated as

“Mashina kecha tuzatildi” or “Ular mashinani kecha tuzatishdi,” depending on stylistic and pragmatic considerations. This indicates that translation is not purely grammatical but also context-dependent.

Overall, the results demonstrate that passive voice in both languages functions as an important grammatical and pragmatic tool, but its realization differs significantly. English favors analytic and structurally consistent passive forms, while Uzbek relies on morphological markers and pragmatic context. These differences highlight the importance of considering both linguistic structure and communicative intent in comparative and translation studies.

CONCLUSIONS AND SUGGESTIONS

In conclusion, this study has demonstrated that passive voice in English and its translation into Uzbek represent a complex linguistic phenomenon that involves not only grammatical structure but also semantic and pragmatic dimensions. The comparative analysis shows that both languages share a common communicative goal, namely foregrounding the patient and backgrounding the agent; however, they differ significantly in how this function is realized in actual language use.

In English, passive constructions are predominantly analytic (be + past participle) and are widely used in academic, scientific, and formal discourse to achieve objectivity, neutrality, and textual cohesion. In contrast, Uzbek expresses passive meaning mainly through morphological markers (-il, -in, -tir, -dir) and auxiliary constructions with *bo'lmoq*, with a stronger tendency to omit the agent or express it indirectly. This reflects both typological differences and discourse preferences in the two languages.

Furthermore, the study highlights that the translation of passive constructions from English into Uzbek is not a purely mechanical process. Instead, it requires various transformation strategies, such as grammatical substitution, transposition, and nominalization, in order to achieve naturalness and pragmatic equivalence. In some cases, passive structures are preserved, while in others they are converted into active constructions depending on the context and stylistic requirements.

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- 13.00.00 Pedagogika fanlari
 - 13.00.01 Pedagogika nazariyasi. Pedagogik ta'limotlar tarixi
 - 13.00.02 Ta'lim va tarbiya nazariyasi va metodikasi (sohalar bo'yicha)
 - 13.00.03 Maxsus pedagogika
 - 13.00.04 Jismoniy tarbiya va sport mashg'ulotlari nazariyasi va metodikasi
 - 13.00.05 Kasb-hunar ta'limi nazariyasi va metodikasi
 - 13.00.06 Elektron ta'lim nazariyasi va metodikasi (ta'lim sohaları va bosqichlari bo'yicha)
 - 13.00.07 Ta'limda menejment
 - 13.00.08 Maktabgacha ta'lim va tarbiya nazariyasi va metodikasi
 - 13.00.09 Ijtimoiy pedagogika
 - 07.00.00 Tarix fanlari
 - 19.00.00 Psixologiya fanlari
 - 01.00.00 Fizika-matematika fanlari
 - 02.00.00 Kimyo fanlari
 - 03.00.00 Biologiya fanlari
 - 09.00.00 Falsafa fanlari
 - 10.00.00 Filologiya fanlari
 - 11.00.00 Geografiya fanlari

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